

D5.3 INTERIM IMPACT ASSESSMENT REPORT

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Abstract	This will be the first of two reports that tracks the impact assessment achieved through direct interactions such as f2f meetings, indirect interactions (ie: tools, services in this case the adoption of the RDA outputs, and financial interactions ie: potential stakeholders engaging in economic exchange with researchers, research contracts or special funding etc.).

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

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Disclaimer

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Definition

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Executive Summary

To be completed when done

1 Introduction

This report draws together threads from all work packages and activities within the RDA Europe 4.0 project and reflects on the impact our support programme has achieved. At this interim stage we are mainly reporting on the measures being monitored and the quantitative outcomes (e.g. membership numbers, event attendance, download figures). We also assess whether our activities seem to be driving the change desired and some elements of qualitative impact are noted. More of these elements will emerge in later stages of the project and beyond.

The key activities reported on include:

- Membership and attendance figures
- Adoption of outputs
- Ambassador programme
- Node network
- Early Career Researcher and Expert Grants
- Communication

The outputs of this analysis will be discussed with RDA global which is currently working on a global RDA impact analysis.

2 Measures to track impact

A number of measures are being monitored to track impact. We began considering all the possible areas in which it would be desirable to understand impact, and then eliminating those where measurement was impractical or not meaningful within the timescale of the project. The proposed aspects were discussed in a face-to-face project meeting in October 2018. We agreed to track a number of quantitative indicators and interactions while also assessing what they achieved. This report is consequently broken down into corresponding sections to collectively assess the net impact of all our activities.

The approach was intended to be modelled on the SIAMPI (Social Impact Methods for research & funding instruments through study of Productive Interactions) work. However, whilst this European project produced an academic article and a project report, neither included something as concrete as a tool or guidelines on how to apply the principles. We interpreted them as:

- Measuring direct interactions
- Indirect interactions (via a tool, service etc)
- financial interactions

The last of these was seen as less relevant in the context of RDA work so effort has focused on measuring direct interactions in terms of membership and event attendance and the more intangible, qualitative impact of our engagement programmes as well as indirect interactions such as web site use.

Quantitative indicators being measured include:

- Membership numbers, per country
- Number of European members holding formal positions e.g. WG/IG Chairs, TAB etc
- Attendance at plenaries

- Attendance at events (including webinars)
- Download and citation figures for Recommendation and Outputs (in Zenodo)
- Website view figures for outputs pages
- Articles published in CODATA special collection (and download figures)
- Number of adoption stories
- Social Media

Qualitative indicators:

- Influence on national data policy
- Input / support to national data programmes
- Breadth / diversity of engagement (e.g. country, discipline, gender, sector)
- Career development and mentorship opportunities
- Efficiencies via outputs adoption

3 Impact in numbers

3.1 European RDA membership

The membership figures for all European countries are available in a [dashboard](#) created by the project to support national nodes. This allows the user to filter the data by country and date to investigate how many members have joined in a given period. The data also categorises members by sector (academia, government, SME).

Figure 1 - membership growth

The total RDA Europe members currently is 4925. This is 59% of global membership. There has been a steady growth since the inception of RDA, with a small peak in March 2017 around the time the plenary took place in Barcelona. The three countries with the largest membership are UK, Germany and France.

3.1.1 Membership within countries with nodes

During the reporting period, RDA Europe members have grown by 891 members from 3404 in end February 2018 to 4295 as of 22 May 2019. This is a 21% increase. Figures for each country with a national node are provided below. These show that many existing nodes have already met or exceeded the KPIs for membership increase, which range from 15% to 25%

and in one case (Ireland) 40% and that community growth is strong in them all. The average increase across countries with nodes is greater than across Europe as a whole.

The four nodes funded in the first wave of the cascading grant (highlighted in orange) have the highest percentage increases, followed by France and Italy which have both have very strong programmes of events and local engagement.

Table 1 - European RDA growth by country

Country	Membership in February 2018	Membership in May 2019	Number of new members	Percentage increase
Austria	55	76	21	38%
Denmark	57	80	23	40%
Finland	147	182	35	24%
France	323	449	126	39%
Germany	470	574	104	22%
Greece	113	134	21	19%
Ireland	138	158	20	14%
Italy	296	395	99	33%
Netherlands	282	346	64	23%
Portugal	55	83	28	51%
Slovenia	9	21	12	133%
Spain	279	329	50	18%
United Kingdom	678	781	103	15%
TOTAL	2902	3608	706	24%

European RDA growth by country ([source](#))

3.1.2 Number of European members attending plenaries

European members are regular attendees at RDA plenaries with over 100 attending in every case. Naturally the most recent plenary to be held in Europe (Berlin) saw a much higher number of attendees, with 458 participants. Members also come from a broad range of

countries, representing most of the member states. The highest attendance usually comes from the UK, Germany, Netherlands and France.

P13 in Philadelphia, USA

435 participants of which 164 from 17 European countries (38%):

Top 10 Countries	#Participants
United Kingdom	38
Germany	34
Netherlands	22
France	14
Finland	10
Italy	10
Norway	6
Austria	4
Belgium	4
Spain	4

P12 in Gaborone, Botswana

841 participants of which 151 from 22 European countries (18%):

Top 10 Countries	#Participants
United Kingdom	40
Germany	32
Netherlands	19
France	12
Italy	9
Finland	8
Austria	5
Belgium	4
Russia	3
Bulgaria	2

P11 in Berlin, Germany

660 participants of which 458 from 22 European countries (69%):

Top 10 Countries	#Participants
Germany	175
United Kingdom	67
France	41

Netherlands	40
Italy	27
Norway	21
Belgium	14

3.2 Number of Europeans part of the RDA Governance

29 May 2019	OAB	TAB	Secretariat	Council
Members	8	14	12	12
EU Members	4	6	8	3
%	50%	43%	67%	25%

It should also be noted that 5 other people attend Council in an ex-officio capacity (the co-chairs of OAB & TAB, and the Secretary-General). 3 of these 5 are currently European. There is a KPI related to this measure (30% of governance to be European) which is comfortably exceeded across the figures above.

Number of European chairs as today: **102**
 Number of Europeans who are WG Chairs: **40**
 Number of Europeans who are IG Chairs: **62**

Continent	IG Chairs	Continent	WG Chairs
Africa	1	Africa	2
Asia	2	Asia	2
EU	62	EU	40
North America	50	North America	24
Oceania	16	Oceania	5
South America	1	South America	2

3.3 Number of adoption stories

The RDA Europe 4.0 project works on inspiring further uptake of RDA outputs by sharing challenges, best practices and lessons learned in the shape of adoption stories, published on the RDA website¹. Below a list with the 7 adoption stories collected, published and disseminated by RDA EU 4.0

- **Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Center (VAMDC, France)** adopted Dynamic Data Citation Recommendation and Scholix. The authors of the adoption story also published an article in the CODATA special collection on RDA: <http://http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-004>

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>

- **French National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA, France)** adopted Wheat Data Interoperability Guidelines, Agrisemantics Working Group recommendations, Recommendations for Implementing a Virtual Layer for Management of the Complete Life Cycle of Scientific Data, 23 Things: Libraries for Research Data, The FAIRsharing Registry and Recommendations and Data Citation of Evolving data.
- **Climate Change Center Austria (CCCA)** adopted the RDA Recommendation on Data Citation of Evolving Data
- **The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Global Science Forum (GSF)** adopted the Income Streams for Data Repositories report produced by the RDA/WDS Publishing Data Cost Recovery for Data Centres Interest Group. This story was coordinated by the Dutch node coordinator DANS.
- The **CoreTrustSeal** adoption story series highlights the certification of 6 repositories around the globe, of which 3 European, namely Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS, Netherlands) Strasbourg astronomical Data Center (CDS, France) and Digital Repository Ireland (DRI, Ireland).

3.4 The Ambassadors programme

The table below highlights a set of statistics that RDA EU 4.0 is collecting and monitoring, related to both the Open call process as well as the appointed Ambassadors. The initial cohort includes 8 Ambassadors covering just as many disciplines; 3 are female and 5 male and come from 6 different countries (both France and Netherlands have 2 grantees):

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance	Disciplines covered
1st wave	17	6	5 Denmark, France, Italy, Slovenia, United Kingdom	2 Female / 4 Male	6 Agricultural Sciences; Earth Sciences / Climate modelling; Engineering/ Renewable Materials; Engineering and Technology / Wind energy; High energy physics/ Fusion; Marine Sciences / Fisheries
Node Ambassadors	-	2	1 Netherlands	1 Female / 1 Male	2 Humanities; Social Sciences

Monitoring the indicators allow us to keep track of the progress as well as making sure there is a balanced distribution of grants in terms of geographical representation, disciplines and gender of the grantees. Disciplines that are under-represented in the RDA were given priority.

3.5 Early Career and Expert programmes

A total of 60+ eligible applications were received and 32 grantees were selected. The table below illustrates the figures in relation to each Plenary and Open Call process:

Ref.	Eligible applications	Number of grantees	Countries represented	Gender balance	Discipline coverage
11 th Plenary, March 2018, Berlin	13	6	5 United Kingdom, Austria, Spain, Greece, Finland	3 Female / 3 Male	1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Humanities/Other humanities 2 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Social Sciences/Sociology
12 th Plenary, Nov 2018, Botswana	29	13	7 Slovenia, Germany, Netherlands, Italy, Austria, Portugal, United Kingdom	7 Female / 6 Male	1 Humanities/History and archaeology 1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Engineering and Technology/Materials engineering 4 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Chemical sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Social Sciences/Educational sciences 2 Social Sciences/Other social sciences
13 th Plenary, April 2019, Philadelphia	29	13	12 Netherlands, Germany, Switzerland, France, Austria, Germany, Portugal, United Kingdom, Greece, Ireland,	6 Female / 7 Male	1 Agricultural Sciences/Agricultural biotechnology 1 Engineering and Technology/Electrical engineering, electronic, engineering, information engineering 1 Medical and Health

			Italy		Sciences/Health sciences 6 Natural Sciences/Computer and information sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Earth and related environmental sciences 1 Natural Sciences/Biological sciences 1 Social Sciences/Educational sciences 1 Social Sciences/Sociology
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The indicators above highlight the project commitment to engage a diverse audience in terms of geographical provenance (13 countries represented) and scientific / disciplinary background (close to 15 disciplines covered). It should also be noted that, although differently balanced in the various call editions, the overall gender ratio is an even split, with 16 females and 16 males.

4 Qualitative indicators - the net effect of activities

4.1 Ambassadors

The Ambassador programme was created to bring representatives from different disciplinary communities into the core work of RDA, and thereby to expand both the reach of RDA's outputs through these disciplines, and to expand the range of disciplines involved directly in the RDA's mission. In addition, the Ambassadors are actively articulating RDA's value proposition and impact for their disciplines.

4.1.1 Ambassadorial work and meeting the discipline gaps

Dr. Ricarda Braukmann - RDA EU Ambassador for Social Sciences published a report that categorises and details the specific benefits of RDA to the Social Sciences: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1401105. This report combined with the Ambassador's other outreach efforts are cited in the case for creating a new Interest Group on Humanities and Social Sciences, the charter for which is currently under review:

<https://rd-alliance.org/groups/social-sciences-humanities-research-data-ig>

4.1.2 Ambassadors and discipline gaps and opportunities

Following the successful example of the Social Sciences report, Ambassadors from the variety of disciplines represented in the first stages of the programme are reflecting on how a similar approach can be taken for other disciplines, to identify, delineate, and map RDA working groups and outputs. The RDA for the Humanities Group is near completion on this task, with the report currently under review, and expected to be published in June 2019.

4.1.3 Creating connections beyond disciplines

Ana Slavec, Ambassador for Engineering/ Renewable Materials, is also co-coordinator of the Open Science working group at The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior

Researchers (Eurodoc). Her work as an Ambassador therefore helps to connect the RDA and Eurodoc, which is a significant step in diversifying the career-stage diversity of RDA's reach.

4.1.4 Engaging with national nodes

Ambassadors have established or leveraged an already established connection with the RDA national nodes, helping to align disciplinary practices with national or regional approaches, creating the data-sharing synergy that is at the heart of RDA's mission. For example, the Ambassadors supported by DANS have made strong connections to the Dutch national node. Similarly, Nikola Vasiljevic (RDA EU Ambassador for Engineering and Technology / Wind energy), is presenting on what RDA can do for engineering as part of the RDA in Denmark national node launch event (14 June 2019).

4.2 Early-career and expert grants

Both the Early Career and Expert grants programmes were designed to support individual participation in the Research Data Alliance. These programmes offer grant winners the opportunity to engage directly with and support the work of RDA Working and Interest Groups, contribute and become a part of the RDA global data sharing community.

The programmes were aligned with both the European project objectives of supporting European participation and contribution to RDA and the RDA global vision of engaging a diversified and inter-generational community.

As in the case of the Ambassadors programme, the Early Career and Expert grants are assessed and progress monitored both in terms of the qualitative and quantitative aspects.

4.2.1 Supporting a diverse, inter-generational community

The two grant programmes complement each other in the effort to foster inter-generational exchange between researchers at different career levels. Case in point, Early Career grantees have been assigned to and encouraged to join the Early Career and Engagement IG and leverage their Mentorship programme to which Expert grantees have signed up as mentors. The initiative brings together senior RDA members and researchers at the beginning of their career and newcomers to RDA.

4.2.2 Early Careers grants as a springboard to actively join the RDA WG and IG

There are several examples of how the Early Career grant program has made a notable impact on the careers of winners, which in turn has benefited the growth of RDA and its impact. For example, several grantees have become chairs of RDA WGs or IGs or have taken on active roles in various groups:

- João Rocha - became chair of the Repository Platforms for Research Data IG, has suggested setting up a WG (driven by the RPRD IG) as a forum for discussion and comparison of research data management platforms
- Kathleen Gregory: has been actively involved with the Data Discovery Paradigms IG, she is co-author on the best practices article published as an output from the IG

- Daniela Hausen has contributed to the Research data management in Engineering IG charter
- Romain David: provide presentations at both SHaring Rewards & Credit IG and Agrisemantics WG meetings during the 13th RDA Plenary - both group activities are connected to his work at INRA and PhD project.

The impact of this is clear: early-career researchers, given the opportunity to attend RDA plenaries and be actively introduced to WGs/IGs through the conditions of their grant, then gain experience and become influencers in their domain (not to mention, they help to grow their communities).

4.2.3 Getting engaged at national level

In their activities report and applications many of the Early Career grantees have mentioned getting involved in node activities (e.g. Joana Rodrigues, Kathleen Gregory, João Rocha, Maja Dolinar, Dorothea Strecker, Martina Trognitz). A few have mentioned this as an easier path to getting engaged in RDA, keeping up with the developments in the field while keeping an eye on the national aspects. Where the Ambassadors help to connect disciplines to national approaches, the Early Career programme helps to bring different generations into the RDA, which contributes to the diversity of ideas, and to RDA's sustainability.

4.2.4 Experts grants contributing to the critical assessment of the work of RDA

Input collected through the reports and contributions from the Expert grantees was taken up as critical feedback on the work of RDA e.g. a taskforce has been set up to look more in detail into operational and organisational aspects of RDA related to quality checks, duration of various steps and processes set out for the group activities.

4.3 Adoption

The adoption of RDA outputs has been promoted in several activities, namely adoption stories, the special collection in the CODATA journal, and most recently adoption grants. Seven adoption stories have been published in this period (See 3.3). These cover the adoption of 11 different recommendations and outputs, with the RDA Recommendation on Data Citation of Evolving Data being the most frequently implemented. This has been adopted in astronomy via the Virtual Atomic and Molecular Data Center (VAMDC), within the French National Institute for Agricultural Research (INRA) and within the Climate Change Center Austria (CCCA). The wide disciplinary and geographical application demonstrates the value and impact of this output. All the adoption stories can be found at: <https://www.rda-alliance.org/recommendations-outputs/adoption-stories>

Thirteen applications were received for adoption grants from nine different countries. A strong range of proposals were put forward, covering a range of outputs and disciplines. The 8 awards made cover a range of outputs and provide many opportunities for impact. As they are only just being contractualized, it is too early to note impact, however much potential exists.

The grant conditions require that award-holders add value to the RDA output by providing a practical use case, a description of benefits of adoption, guidelines that can assist others in adoption, and/or constructive criticism and recommendations for improvement if the planned adoption posed any challenges. These guidelines and feedback will help the outputs achieve

broader impact.

Three projects are adopting “Workflows for Research Data Publishing” so will be encouraged to collaborate, and several others are adopting outputs used previously such as the Repository Audit and Certification guidelines, 23 things, the FAIRsharing registry and the Metadata Standards Directory. The RDA network will be used to share experiences and support those undertaking new projects.

4.4 Nodes

- TO BE ADDED IN THE FINAL REPORT

4.4.1 Activating and growing the community

As discussed earlier, nodes are supporting and growing national RDA communities through local programmes of outreach, dissemination and engagement. The growth rates reported over the project period to date demonstrate a strong interest in

4.4.2 Engaging with and contributing to national policies

[examples from France, Ireland,...]

4.4.3 Fostering and documenting adoption of RDA outputs

Events and training

To date, 21 events have been run by the RDA Europe nodes, including webinars, workshops and conferences.

Webinars run by nodes include a series of four in 2018 organised by the Italian node in collaboration with OpenAIRE and the Italian Open Science Support Group, which attracted over 350 participants in total. Topics covered included open science, research data management, FAIR data and data management plans.² This series helped to grow membership of the Italian node and another series of three webinars is currently underway covering other data-related topics such as data stewardship.³

Participation to external events

Future plans

Feedback on events

Survey⁴

² <https://rd-alliance.org/group/rda-italy/wiki/open-science-webinar-series-2018>

³ <https://rd-alliance.org/group/rda-italy/wiki/open-science-webinar-series-2019>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe-national-nodes-community-survey>

4.5 Communications

The RDA Europe 4.0 communication, marketing & stakeholder engagement strategy has a twofold objective: on the one hand, **maximising the visibility** and ensuring uptake of the outputs of RDA - the Research Data Alliance, on the other, **ensuring engagement** of and contribution by European stakeholders via a series of cascading grant programmes and beyond. With this aim in mind Four different RDA Europe 4.0 Outreach & Communication campaigns were designed and are being carried out:

1. Communication and promotion of RDA Outputs
2. Communication & promotion of RDA Europe National Nodes Network
3. Communication and promotion of RDA European open calls for individuals
4. RDA Europe Events & webinars

In these campaigns a number of communication and dissemination activities have been carried out. Impact of these activities is measured by their visibility and engagement rates through the RDA channels.

The growing RDA Social Media community

On Twitter the RDA Europe social media community grew with 40 %, the RDA global community with over 31% over the period of M1-M16.

Top performing tweets

Messages on RDA outputs and RDA EU 4.0 calls have gained a lot of visibility. The following messages have had between 4400 - 5700 impressions. Both content on RDA Outputs and RDA EU calls show high impact.

Top Performing Tweets

Top Tweet earned 5,725 impressions

+5700 Impressions

Experts in #FAIRdata @FAIRsFAIR @GOFAIR forces to bring the #GE... Maturity Indicators for #... Certification of #Repositor... Come and join us! Read the webinar details bit.ly/2T5Y533 pic.twitter.com/toBssZAk9

Top Tweet earned 4,460 impressions

+4600 Impressions

@RDA_Europe Call for application 27. Don't miss your chance with the RDA in transition and implementing the RDA... bit.ly/2ThmhWY pic.twitter.com/NzmAovmHN

Top Tweet earned 4,435 impressions

+4400 Impressions

Meet the @RDA_Europe grant winners joining the meeting in Philadelphia in April 2019. Stay tuned... For now, read this bit.ly/2... Inspire & share your ideas @RDA #CascadingGrants bit.ly/2SvO3Wb pic.twitter.com/talV96Kt11

Top performing tweets in the global RDA community

Top Tweet earned 5,212 impressions

+5212 Impressions

Stay tuned as today is the 13th #RDAPlenary. Data p... researchers, industry leader... & policymakers from all disci... geographies will reconvene from Philadelphia, US.

Check the programme bit.ly/crIM30ohlaX pic.twitter.com/Wg1yAkaXCh

Top Tweet earned 5,100 impressions

+5100 Impressions

We are very pleased to welcome the Turing Institute @turing to the RDA community. We have joined @resdatall as a member! They will work on #standards and protocols technologies. Keep the #RD... growing! rd-alliance.org/alan-turing-in... pic.twitter.com/mj7uhC6HTB

Top media Tweet earned 3,329 impressions

+3329 Impressions

@CODATANews CIP n... Collection on Research... Results. Submit a high qu... describing the latest results... or Interest Groups or on use cases adopting #RDAoutputs bit.ly/2Va7iX pic.twitter.com/CbXzkvbgON

Multipliers in the social media community

Amongst the connections that count (network multipliers/influencers)

 Ivan Zassoursky @zasursky <small>FOLLOWS YOU</small> 108K Followers	 EUinmyRegion @EUinmyRegion <small>FOLLOWS</small> 74.3K Followers	 Michael Glock Ph.D. @DrMichaelGlock <small>FOLLOWS YOU</small> 16.8K Followers	 UNICEF Innocenti @UNICEFInnocenti <small>FOLLOWS</small> 14.1K Followers
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Amongst the connections that count (network multipliers/influencers)

<p>9.2K Followers</p> <p>Wiley Open Research @WileyOpen FOLLOWS YOU</p>			
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Newsletters

The numbers of European and global newsletters and announcements sent to both communities. The average opening rate is 25%, since March 2018 the number of opened emails is 92.727.

Newsletter category	Amount M1-M18
RDA Announcements	34
RDA EU announcement	16
RDA Europe Node Announcement	3
RDA Global Newsletters	14

13 MAY 2019 **RDA Europe Newsletter: Check the closing soon Ambassador Call and opportunities in the calls for new Nodes, Experts and ECRs**

Last days to apply to the RDA Europe Domain Ambassadors programme

Are you working on the vanguard of data activities in a specific research domain or cluster of domains? Would you like to work together with the RDA in transferring the knowledge and implementing the RDA data solutions within your domain community? Submit your thought-provoking application to the second and last wave of RDA Europe Ambassador Grants Call by 20 May 17.00 CET [here](#).

Apply for the RDA Europe Grants for Early Careers and Experts to join P14 in Helsinki

RDA continues its series of support programmes for data researchers and practitioners and is now running open calls to facilitate participation of 9 RDA Early Career Researchers and 7 Expert RDA members to the 14th RDA Plenary meeting in Helsinki. Work with the RDA community on global data sharing at P14: Apply by August 13 August 17.00 CEST

- RDA EU ECR grant
- RDA EU Expert grant

Read [here](#) about the experiences of the ECR and Expert grantees that attended P13 in Philadelphia.

Webinars

The RDA Europe 4.0 organised and promoted webinars were 7 in total and gathered 164

participants.

Name	date	participants
Webinar for Nodes	15/11	10
RDA Europe Ambassador programme - The What, Why and the How?	27/11	38
RDA Regional Engagement 5 December Webinar	05/12	10
RDA Europe Early Career and Expert grants – Q&A webinar	22/01	20
The What, Why and How - RDA Europe 4.0 Adoption Grants	21/02	43
RDA Europe grants for new nodes: How to apply and join the existing network	07/03	16
RDA Output Adoption Webinar Series: Outputs to Support Reproducible Health Research	22/03	27
	tot	164

Video's

Video	Aim	Impact by number of views
<p>RDA in-one-word</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BdD2NTytb8Q</p>	Interviews at P13 to increase visibility of RDA and the community.	129
<p>Adopting RDA outputs</p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dvv530p6VBU</p>	Raise awareness on adoption of RDA outputs and the call for adoption stories	64
P14 promotion	Promote RDA P14 in Helsinki	40

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FsvOOfxDXQE		

Adoption stories

The series of adoption stories have dedicated page, with promotional video on adopting RDA outputs and a call for adoption stories. The page has received 775 views since it was created in October 2018.

The table below shows the visibility of each of the 6 published stories at the date of writing of this report.

Story	Publication	Unique page views
Data Standards For Agriculture: INRA Adoption Of RDA Outputs	January 2019	285
Implementing RDA outputs for Scholarly Communication	October 2018	164
Improving Citation of evolving data in distributed asynchronous infrastructures	December 2018	112
Towards Sustainable Research Data Repositories	April 2019	36
Dynamic Data Citation For Frequently Modifying High Resolution Climate Data	May 2019	18

The statistics below show that the promotion around the publication of the stories increase visibility of the adoption stories and with it the visibility of RDA outputs adopted.

Publications in Journals

Codata: <https://datascience.codata.org/collections/special/research-data-alliance-results/>

Plos: <https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1006038>

Progress towards expected impacts

- Abbreviated summary of progress towards the six key impacts listed in [progress report](#)

TO BE COMPLETED IN THE FINAL REPORT